

DEVELOPMENT OF BIRD-MIMETIC SPAN-WISE CAMBERED CARBON/EPOXY SPAR STRUCTURE FOR FLAPPING WING OF FLYING ROBOT

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1 Introduction

In recent years, a number of research have been conducted to study flapping-wing air vehicles. The development of flapping-wing micro air vehicle, particularly, has been under the spotlight along with the investigation of nature's flyers, in particular insects. The studies have been attempting to mimic the flight of insects and birds which is based on the principle of biomimetics. It is a tool that involves the abstraction of good design from nature [1]. Nature serves as a viable model, as a measure and as a mentor of imitations by humans [2]. It may represent the imitation of nature's method, designs, or processes which is synchronized by the human capabilities to adapt. Thus, the various principles of nature's flyers and the mimicking of the various working principles of those species become the focus on the biomimetic research on flapping-wing micro air vehicle.

To mimic the whole bird wing structure for the wing structure of the flying robot is unfavorable. Therefore, simplification of the wing is made to investigate certain features of the wing to the aerodynamic performance of the flying robot, as shown in Fig. 1. The properties of this 50-cm flying robot are given in Tab. 1.

2 Designs

2.1 Materials and methods

Layers of uni-directional carbon/epoxy prepreg and fabric are fabricated and reinforced through heating to create the wing structure, as shown in Fig. 2.

Transparent plastic layer is used for the skin of the wing bones. The features that are going to be analyzed are camber and taper ratio.

Fig. 1. Hanwha Corporation flapping wing vehicle model

Tab. 1. Properties of the flying robot

Parameters	Specification
Wing Span	50 cm
Weight	86 g (Battery: 300mA) 110 g (Battery: 800mA)
Flight Duration	20 min (Battery: 300mA) 60 min (Battery: 800mA)
Payload	25 g
Design Flight Speed	8 m/s
Stroke Angle	Upward: 35.2 deg Downward: 0 deg
Flight Flapping Frequency	13 – 18 Hz
Gear Reduction Ratio	12:1
Advance Ratio	1

Uni-direction (UPN116B)– 250mm
Uni-direction (UPN116B)– 250mm
Uni-direction (UPN116B) – 50mm
Uni-direction (UPN116B) – 100mm
Uni-direction (UPN116B) – 150mm
Uni-direction (UPN116B) – 200mm
Fabric (WSN1K-B) – 250mm
Uni-direction (UPN116B) – 200mm
Uni-direction (UPN116B) – 150mm
Uni-direction (UPN116B) – 100mm
Uni-direction (UPN116B) – 50mm
Uni-direction (UPN116B)– 250mm
Uni-direction (UPN116B)– 250mm

Fig. 2. Lay-up composite structure

To test the effects of the span-wise cambered spar to the aerodynamic forces, a series of wings with varying values of flexural stiffness EI are made. The example of the fabricated wing spar with different taper ratio and camber can be seen in Fig. 3. Variation of camber of the wing structure Fig. 3. The final shape of the wing can be seen in Fig. 4.

Fig. 3. Variation of camber of the wing structure

2.2 Experimental Methods

2.2.1 Measurement of wing stiffness

To measure the stiffness E of the wing types, a custom-built wing bending apparatus is used.

Connecting a strain gauge to the surface of the flexible beam which is mounted on a micrometer stage, the distance of the deflection can be controlled. This apparatus can measure the force required to bend the wings bent at a certain design.

Fig. 4. Wing Structure

2.2.2 Force measurement

A flapper system is designed and fabricated to characterize the aerodynamic effects of the wing structure. In the experiments, the flapper is used to see how rigidity affects the performance of the wing. Only the forces perpendicular and parallel to the wing surface are measured from the load cell attached to the system.

The experiments were performed in a low-speed wind tunnel located in the Aerodynamic Analysis & High Speed Experiments Laboratory at Konkuk University. The wind tunnel is a subsonic, closed return wind tunnel with the test section dimension of 1 m high \times 1 m wide \times 3.5 m long. The experiment configuration is shown by Fig. 5 and Fig. 6.

Based on the design parameters that is given in Tab. 2, there were 9 different wing spar made for experiment. Thus, including the original wing spar, there are total 10 wings investigated in this study. The summary of the design matrix is given in Tab. 3. During the experiments, the flapping frequency of the mechanism is adjustable by changing the output voltage of the DC power supply. The aerodynamic forces (lift and drag/thrust) acting on the experimented wings were measured by a 3-axis force-moment load cell (Curiosity Technology, CMAS121-5L). The precision of the load cell is about ± 0.05 kgf of the full scale (5 kgf).

Tab. 2. Design parameters of wings

Parameters		Specification
Taper Ratio		0.43 (1)
		0.54 (2)
		1 (3)
Dimension (mm)	Root	1.75 x 1.8 (1)
		0.75 x 1.8 (1)
	Tip	0.95 x 1.8 (2)
		1.75 x 1.8 (3)
Weight (g)		0.8 (1)
		0.9 (2)
		1.1 (3)
Curvature		5.2×10^{-4} (1)
		10.3×10^{-4} (2)
Material		Carbon/epoxy

During the experiments, the output signals were scanned at 1000 Hz for 60 seconds, similar to the method used by Hu et al. [3]. Only the time-averaged lift and thrust (or drag) data will be shown to assess the influence of taper ratio and camber flexibility to the aerodynamic force. The result is then filtered using a low-pass filter and converted to lift and drag components in the inertial coordinates [4].

Tab. 3. Wing design matrix

Spar	Taper Ratio	Root	Tip	Weight
1	1	1	1	1
2	2	1	2	2
3	3	1	3	3
4	1	1	1	1
5	2	1	2	2
6	3	1	3	3
7	1	1	1	1
8	2	1	2	2
9	3	1	3	3
10*	1	-	-	2

*original spar, circle cross-section ($\varnothing=1.8\text{mm}$)

3 Experimental results and discussions

The wings were tested in different forward flight speed (i.e., the incoming flow velocity). It was changed from 5 to 10 m/s. The orientation angle was changed from 0 degrees to 20 degrees.

Following the work of Ho et. al. [5], a non-dimensional parameter, advance ratio, J , is used to

characterize the measurement data of the wings. Advance ratio, J , which is defined as the ratio of forward flight speed (i.e., incoming flow velocity) to the wingtip velocity during flight can be expressed as:

$$J = \frac{\text{forward flight speed}}{\text{wingtip velocity}} = \frac{V_{\infty}}{2fA} \quad (1)$$

where f is the wing flapping frequency, and A is the peak-to-peak displacement of the wing during flapping flight. The flow around a flapping wing can be considered quasi-steady when $J > 1.0$, while $J < 1.0$ corresponds to unsteady state regime.

Fig. 5. Wind tunnel setup

Fig. 6. Experiment setup

4 Concluding Remarks

In this work, the aerodynamic performance of the flapping with vehicle with different wing parameters has been investigated. An experimental setup in the wind tunnel is used to measure the aerodynamic forces of the vehicle in different flight conditions.

The main parameters that become the focus of study are taper ratio and camber of the wings to determine the flexibility of the wings. With different wing structure flexibilities, the performances of the wings were investigated and gave ways for the optimization of the wing design.

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